

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that builds an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

**2025: a successful
year for EXA4MIND**

By
Jan Martinovič, EXA4MIND project coordinator
Stephan Hachinger, Science and Co-design Coordinator of EXA4MIND

2025: a successful year for EXA4MIND

Written by Jan Martinovič, EXA4MIND project coordinator & Stephan Hachinger, EXA4MIND science and co-design coordinator.

Dear reader,

We are entering the final phase of our journey with the EXA4MIND project. The vision of building a flexibly deployable Extreme Data Platform that integrates advanced data storage systems with powerful computing infrastructures is

becoming a reality. Over the past year, **we have reached significant milestones**, bringing us closer to delivering cutting-edge solutions for Extreme Data management and analytics.

We would like to thank the entire [consortium](#) for their hard work and contributions, which have helped the project move forward.

[Read the full editorial](#)

Events

EXA4MIND at EBDVF 2025

The European Big Data Value Forum ([EBDVF](#)) 2025 took place in Copenhagen from 12 to 14 November. As part of our sponsorship activities, **EXA4MIND had a booth at EBDVF**, where we shared the project's progress and main achievements to date with hundreds of visitors and participants.

As in the [previous edition](#), **EXA4MIND also hosted a session** with the [DataNexus cluster](#), continuing to address a topic that remains largely unexplored, even within the big data and AI community: extreme data and its challenges. The session was moderated by Nuria de Lama ([IDC](#)) and Janine Gehrig Lux ([Barcelona Supercomputing Centre – BSC](#)), and featured the following speakers: Eduardo Quiñones ([BSC](#)), Pedro García ([Rovira i Virgili University](#)), Junaid Ahmed Khan ([University of Bologna](#)), and Stephan Hachinger ([Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#)).

VIDEO | DataNexus highlights at EBDVF 2025

On 13 November, **EXA4MIND** had the pleasure of co-hosting and co-organising a **DataNexus session** as part of the European Big Data Value Forum 2025 programme. [EXA4MIND](#), [EXTRACT](#), [Graph-Massivizer](#) and [NearData](#) presented real-world case studies demonstrating the tangible impact of next-generation workflows, AI integration and high-performance data platforms across domains ranging from energy and manufacturing to smart cities and crisis management.

We are very happy to share a **video** prepared by our communication and dissemination partner, [AUSTRALO](#), showcasing the session's highlights and featuring interviews with the people who made it possible.

EXA4MIND at SC25

St. Louis was the place to be from 16 to 21 November as the global high-performance computing (HPC) community gathered for an exciting week of sessions, keynote speakers, and top-tier networking. The Supercomputing Conference ([SC](#)) 2025 brought together thousands of scientists, engineers, researchers, educators, programmers, and developers to learn, share, and innovate. The **EXA4MIND project proudly made its mark at this prestigious event.**

[Discover more](#)

Scientific contributions

A new EXA4MIND-related poster is now available

The new scientific poster, 'Integrated Database of Force-Field Parameters, Experimental Measurements and Molecular Dynamics Simulations as a Tool for Force Field Development', related to the EXA4MIND project, is **now publicly available**.

Written by Vojtěch Mlýnský of the [Institute of Biophysics at the Czech Academy of Sciences](#) and the IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center, it was **presented at the 14th European Conference on Computational and Theoretical Chemistry (EuChemS CompChem 2025)**, organised by the European Chemical Society (EuChemS).

[View and download it](#)

Project graphic materials

Now available: The updated EXA4MIND trifold

The updated **EXA4MIND 2025 trifold** is now available to view and download on the project's Zenodo page. This concise brochure outlines the mission, vision, and impact of EXA4MIND.

It also **provides an overview of EXAKI**, the EXA4MIND knowledge centre, which supports researchers, SMEs, and industry professionals by offering training, documentation, and practical guidance on deploying extreme data technologies. Finally, the brochure summarises EXA4MIND's diverse scientific, industrial, agricultural, and health data use cases, showcasing its impact across disciplines.

[View and download it](#)

Mark your calendars

List of upcoming events

EXA4MIND is about to conclude a pivotal year in its history. During this time, the consortium partners have demonstrated the tangible results of their research and development work from 2023 to end of 2025. Thanks to the project extension, **EXA4MIND will have a strong presence at national and international events in the first months of 2026**, which will be crucial to our commitment to open science.

- **SCA/HPCAsia 2026**: The Supercomputing Asia (SCA) and the International Conference on High Performance Computing in Asia-Pacific Region (HPCAsia) will take place in Osaka, Japan, from 26 to 29 January 2026.
 - **ITS European Congress**: The 17th ITS European Congress will take place in Istanbul, Turkey, from 27 to 29 April 2026, under the theme 'Bridging Innovation: Integrated, safe and seamless mobility'.
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